

ESTIMATION OF IODINE IN PERIODATES.

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A direct method for the estimation of iodine in the periodates, which give up the whole of iodine on heating, has been described. The results obtained by the new method have been compared with those obtained by Kimmin's method as modified by Partington and Bahl

The estimation of iodine in periodates is carried out by the usual iodometric methods with slight modifications (Partington and Bahl, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1087; Bahl and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 269). Most of the periodates liberate the whole of their iodine content on strong heating and in such cases it has been found to be more convenient and accurate to determine its value directly.

P R O C E D U R E .

A preliminary experiment was performed by heating a small quantity of the periodate in a hard glass test tube till the whole of iodine was given out. The absence of any violet vapours of iodine even on the addition of a little concentrated sulphuric acid to the residue ensures complete evolution of iodine on heating.

The weighed salt (0.1 to 0.2 g.) was taken into a hard glass test tube, the open end of which was fused with a tube provided with two small bulbs. This in turn was connected to a bubbler containing a concentrated solution of potassium iodide. The tube with the bulbs was kept cool by covering it with a cotton pad soaked in cold water. The periodate lying in the end of the tube was strongly heated to ensure complete decomposition. It was disconnected from the bubbler and the iodine condensed in the cooler parts of the tube was washed down in a conical flask with a solution of potassium iodide. The dissolved iodine was titrated against a standard solution of sodium thiosulphate.

The table below shows the comparative values of iodine estimated by (a) Kimmin's method as modified by Partington and Bahl and (b) the direct method.

TABLE I.

Salts.	Sample	Iodine by (a).	Iodine by (b)	Calc. value.
Cerium mesoperiodate tetra- hydrate, $\text{CeIO}_6, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1	30.41%	30.26%	30.20%
	2	29.82	30.10	
Yttrium diorthoperiodate with 11 molecules of water, $\text{Y}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13}, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1	25.40	25.27	25.03
	2	25.20	25.23	
Yttrium mesoperiodate tetrahydrate, $\text{YIO}_6, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1	33.50	33.49	33.54
	2	33.20	33.38	
Quaternary cupric paraperiodate monohydrate, $\text{Cu}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$.	1	36.20	36.03	36.17
	2	36.51	36.41	
Cupric paraperiodate heptahydrate, $\text{Cu}_5\text{IO}_6\text{I}_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1	29.10	28.99	28.45
	2	29.12	29.04	
Cupric paraperiodate pentahydrate $\text{Cu}_5 \cdot \text{IO}_6\text{I}_2, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1	29.45	29.71	29.75

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